

INNOVATIVE CRITERIAL ASSESSMENT METHODS BASED ON MODERN EDUCATION CONTENT (CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM)

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ABSTRACT

This article demonstrates innovative criterial assessment methods based on modern education content through help of credit-module system. The expected results of the system, a credit-module system in Uzbekistan will be explained below.

Introduction.

Nowadays, the world is changing day by day and education system is not an exception as well as. There are different innovative criterial assessment methods based on modern education content through help of credit-module system. The process of organizing education that is a model of assessment based on a set of modular technologies of teaching and credit means the credit- module system. Two basic issue of credit – module system exists. They are given below.

- Ensuring student's independent task
- Assessment of students' knowledge with its rating

Study load here it means time that is spend by students in order to master particular field of study means Credit. Both a minimum time for students' normative documents and independent task is a credit. After finishing a course and final exam a credit is given to student.

The first introduced place of Credit-module is USA in the 18th and 19th century. Charles William Eliot, the president of Harvard University introduced the concept of the "credit hour". That's why a system of credit hours was introduced in 1870-1880 years. Studying with the credit system allows students to study independently.

There are several functions of a credit-module system. Below they will be counted.

- educational process via modular organization
- identifying the value of one subject, credit
- evaluating students' knowledge according to their rating points.
- giving a chance to students in order to create their own curriculum
- boost the percentage of sharing independent task in the process of education
- comfort system in labor market for changing demand of scientists

Above mentioned factors include both teaching new educational technologies and increase the rate of independence of students. That all aimed the professional development and maturity of students in the process of acquiring knowledge.

What about a module. A module means that it is a curriculum that containing several subjects and course. Students will learn a course independently and do task individually. With the help of it, teachers could give live and audio lectures and organize appropriate tasks for learners.

According to foreign scientists the credit – module system consists 2-4 modules in per semester. In order to become a specialist, students should learn information and put them into practice as well. Without practice students can not succeed.

Module based curriculum will be developed with some stages.

- full openness of learning aims and tasks
- requirement of qualification of students at the beginning and at the end of the course.
- a summary or in other words the syllabus of each subject is included in the module.
- plans of the lessons, assignments for independent tasks and others also include in the module.
- summary of teaching and some methods of it are given the module as well.

The student takes the responsibility, resolving all issues and independence of education with the help of a credit-module system. In other word students will become more independent compare to past times.

In higher educations, the number of credits for each semester and total amount for full semester will be gained by students. Unlike current curriculum, in the credit system, additionally, compulsory subjects, elective subjects are also added to students' individual scheme. Students will not be dropped from courses if they are not able to collect all credits from the subjects. They just are given a chance to retake an examination of that subject. Diploma of higher education is given when the completion of required credits is given by students.

Conclusion.

Taking all into consideration, a credit module system plays a crucial role in innovative criterial assessment methods. With the help of it just the rate of independent study is increasing and students are aware of their task efficiently. They can monitor and observe their own chance and assignment on time and whenever they need. Thus the pursuit of innovation, the continuation of efforts toward the reformation in higher education system is a true decision in all aspects.

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